

EXPLORING TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF PERSONALIZED LEARNING: A STUDY AMONG PRIMARY AND SECONDARY TEACHERS

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Abstract

Personalized learning has emerged as a recurring topic in any discussion on curricular innovation, aimed at ensuring quality, equity, and excellence of the educational systems in the evolving global context of the 21st century. It is increasingly evident and widely acknowledged that the standardizing approach of the traditional educational systems is insufficient to meet the diverse array of needs of today's students in educational institutions.

Recently, a significant number of countries (such as Canada, the US, Finland, New Zealand, and the UK, among others) have included the personalized learning approach into their primary and secondary education curricula. Implementing personalized learning entails not only addressing the personal, social, and cultural characteristics of students and their associated needs but also attending to their interests, goals, and individual learning preferences. Additionally, a wide range of governmental organizations (e.g., the U.S. Department of Education, 2016; OECD, 2006; UNESCO, 2017) highlight the potential of this learning approach to address or at least mitigate the unequal learning outcomes of many students and their lack of engagement in school activities.

However, as noted by several authors (Cuban, 2018; Zhang et al., 2020), personalized learning is a term surrounded by controversy, with definitions that diverge significantly. On one hand, some authors perceive personalized learning as a teacher-centered approach, prioritizing the adaptation or individualization of learning activities and content to student's performance. On the other hand, other authors (Bray & McClaskey, 2015; Coll, 2018), perceive personalized learning as a student-centered approach which empowers students to define their own learning goals and needs, thereby providing them with a level of autonomy and decision-making in their learning process.

In Spain, the recent curriculum reform adopts a competency-based approach and promotes personalized learning with the aim of preparing students for present-day challenges. Given the wide variation in definitions and implementation models on personalized learning, the Spanish curriculum reform presents significant challenges for school management teams, the teaching staff, and administration. To implement these new educational practices, tailored support and guidance are essential, which will necessarily vary depending on educational projects, socioeconomic contexts, and the characteristics of professionals in the schools. Within this framework, it is necessary to explore how teachers conceptualize these practices in order to tailor the support and assistance they require.

With this purpose in mind, this study aims to explore teachers' perceptions regarding the impact that different personalized learning strategies may have on student engagement in school activities, and consequently, on their learning outcomes. The work presented here has been undertaken as part of a research project called by the Ministry of Science and Innovation and funded by the State Research Agency of Spanish government (Reference: PID2020-116223RB-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033).

To achieve this goal, we have designed a questionnaire for this study to evaluate teachers' perceptions of personalized learning. This questionnaire comprises three sections, each consisting of a Likert scale with four points. The sections aim to explore their sociodemographic data (8 questions), their perception of the level of student engagement and participation (13 questions), and their opinion on the implementation of

various personalized learning strategies in the classroom (50 questions). These strategies include, for example, working with and from the interests of students, the connection between school and non-school learning experiences, or the reflection on their own learning process, among others.

We gathered the answers of 258 teachers from 14 different educational institutions within the same territory. Some of these institutions have a long-standing tradition of implementing personalized learning strategies in their regular practices, while others have minimal or non-existent emphasis on these strategies. Furthermore, the institutions vary in terms of educational level (primary, secondary), ownership (public, private), and size.

The results reveal significant differences in teachers' perceptions based on educational level, socioeconomic status, and the size of the institution, as well as some personal variables such as age, gender, or teaching experience. Finally, implications of the overall results are discussed from the perspective of supporting and accompanying teachers and institutions in enhancing their practices based on personalized learning.

Keywords: Personalized learning, Teachers' perceptions, Curriculum reform

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